

The Music Encoding Initiative: Its Generation Workflows

Kévin Roger

Université de Lorraine – CRULH (Centre de Recherche Universitaire Lorrain d’Histoire)

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Abstract

This article explores the Music Encoding Initiative (MEI) by examining the workflows that support its generation and manipulation within musicological research. Created in response to the absence of a standard for encoding musical works, MEI has evolved into a powerful, flexible XML framework capable of representing not only Western common music notation but also specialised systems such as mensural, neumatic and tablature notations. This study underscores how the choice of workflow is never neutral and profoundly shapes the quality, sustainability and interoperability of encoded data. The study analyses three principal modes of generating MEI files—via web applications like Verovio and MEI Garage, through integrated software solutions such as MuseScore and Sibelius (enhanced by plug-ins) and using programmatic approaches that rely on command-line tools or programming libraries. Each method presents distinct advantages and limitations, depending on the user’s technical expertise, the complexity of the repertoire and the scale of the project. Beyond generation, the article also addresses tools for enriching and editing MEI files, from metadata completion with MerMEId to more advanced, interactive environments, like Mei-Friend, which combine score visualisation with direct XML editing. Special attention is given to the encoding of early music, highlighting initiatives that adapt MEI to the complexities of historical notations. The article emphasises that adopting MEI is not simply a technical choice but ultimately one that entails significant human and scholarly considerations. It calls for broader training and the thoughtful integration of automated workflows to ensure that digital music editions are both robust and aligned with open science principles.

Keywords: musicology, MEI, XML, music editing, encoding

Résumé

Cet article explore la Music Encoding Initiative (MEI) en examinant les workflows qui soutiennent sa génération et sa manipulation dans la recherche musicologique. Depuis sa création pour combler l'absence d'un standard d'encodage des œuvres musicales, la MEI a évolué en un puissant cadre XML, à la fois souple et performant, capable de représenter non seulement la notation musicale occidentale standard, mais aussi des systèmes spécialisés tels que les notations mensuralistes, neumatiques et les tablatures. Cette étude souligne que le choix du workflow n'est jamais neutre : il influence en profondeur la qualité, la pérennité et l'interopérabilité des données encodées. Sont analysés trois modes principaux de génération de fichiers MEI : des applications web comme Verovio et MEI Garage, des solutions logicielles intégrées telles que MuseScore et Sibelius (enrichies par des plug-ins) et des approches programmatiques reposant sur des outils en ligne de commande ou des bibliothèques logicielles. Chaque méthode présente des avantages et des limites propres, selon l'expertise technique de l'utilisateur, la complexité du répertoire et l'ampleur du projet. Au-delà de la génération, l'article aborde également les outils permettant d'enrichir et d'éditer les fichiers MEI, depuis la saisie des métadonnées avec MerMEId jusqu'à des environnements interactifs plus avancés comme Mei-Friend, qui associent visualisation de la partition et édition XML directe. Une attention particulière est portée à l'encodage des musiques anciennes, en mettant en lumière des initiatives qui adaptent la MEI aux complexités des notations historiques. L'article insiste sur le fait qu'adopter la MEI n'est pas un simple choix technique, mais implique des considérations humaines et scientifiques importantes. Il plaide pour un élargissement de la formation et une intégration réfléchie des workflows automatisés afin que les éditions musicales numériques soient à la fois solides et conformes aux principes de la science ouverte.

Mots-clés : musicologie, MEI, XML, édition musicale, encodage

1. Introduction

Since the 1990s, the issue of digital formats for music editing has gradually become a thorny one in musicological research. Although it is still little explored in musicological literature, the lack of interoperability attributable to the diversity of software is increasingly being addressed within scientific projects. This is because the choice of formats inevitably influences the degree to which data can be exchanged, reused and preserved. As current digital policies rightly favour a FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) approach, this choice also conditions a project's adherence to the digital humanities and, more broadly, to open science (Wilkinson et al. 2016). The recent announcement by MakeMusic that it will no longer be developing its famous Finale software is just one example of the problems of sustainability raised by proprietary tools in musicology.¹

Technical and ethical imperatives generally contribute to the rise of free standards. This is how the Music Encoding Initiative (MEI) came into being in 1999, at the instigation of Perry Roland (University of Virginia). Faced with the absence of a standardised format for encoding semantic, symbolic and editorial information about a musical work, Roland suggested an XML schema be developed, which quickly became the MEI standard. The acronym refers directly to the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI), whose philosophy and technical framework serve as an inspiration (Wilson 2020).² MEI is the result of international collaborations in the early 2000s and aims to provide musicology with a common and shared format – the cornerstone of a unified digital music landscape (Roland 2000; 2002).

Almost 20 years after the first formulations of MEI were completed, the role of this format in musicology is still subject to some debate. While there is a consensus as to its necessity and sustainability, its generation processes still tend to dissuade some researchers from using it. The reason for this reluctance is partly linked to the question of the workflows required to work with MEI. Since this language is foremost an XML specification, its use is dependent on the various ways of manipulating it: conversion, export, transformation, etc. These methods, often wrongly considered as anecdotal, are actually pivotal. They ensure a rigorous creation chain, avoiding technical inconsistencies between the various stages of the editing process. Understanding the various workflows – their principles, advantages and disadvantages – means mastering the entire MEI ecosystem and adapting it to a specific project or musical repertoire. This is even more important given that MEI is so flexible that it can incorporate not only the acoustic and interpretative aspects of

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1. See “The End of Finale”, letter dated 26th August 2024 from the President of MakeMusic: <https://www.finalemusic.com/blog/end-of-finale-new-journey-dorico-letter-from-president/>.
 2. <https://tei-c.org/>

many musical genres and styles but also metadata, variants and annotations. Moreover, one of MEI's key strengths lies in its ability to accommodate diverse systems beyond standard Western music notation, including mensural notation, neumes or tablature (Roland, Hankinson, and Pugin 2014; De Luca and Bain 2019; Desmond et al. 2022). These are not marginal cases: they represent entire fields of musicological research that require tailored encoding strategies. Therefore, the choice of tools, including workflows, has a major influence on the way in which musical information is preserved, represented and, consequently, disseminated.

In the following, I propose these workflows be considered not simply as neutral procedures but as essential mediations shaping the reliability and sustainability of MEI in research contexts. This article seeks to examine how the diversity of available tools influences the practical adoption of MEI and what this implies for different scholarly profiles. By adopting a more analytical perspective, the aim is to tackle the following questions: What are the technical and human obstacles to implementing MEI workflows? How do different tools affect the quality and interoperability of the output? How can researchers choose the workflow best suited to their corpus, music notation type or technical skills? Faced with the economic tensions that impact social science and humanities institutes, it seems essential to assess digital workflows in relation to the profiles and backgrounds of current research staff (researchers, research support staff and lecturers) and their multiple working contexts. Because a human being stands behind every machine, its input is shaped by their choices and, even more importantly, their expertise (Moe 2021; Geertinger 2021).

The first part of this article focuses on workflows related to the conversion of MEI files. For the sake of clarity, the workflows discussed will be presented in the following order, according to the most common modes of interaction: web applications (Verovio and MEI Garage); software and plug-ins (Sibelius and MuseScore); and programmatic conversion tools (command lines, Application Programming Interfaces [APIs] and libraries). A subsection will also be dedicated to the specific case of early music notations (the Mensural, Neumes and Tablature modules). To evaluate the different workflows for generating MEI files, three levels of evaluation have been defined: technical (integrity of the format, preservation of metadata, etc.), scalable (performance and practicality as a function of data density) and ergonomic (accessibility, user-friendliness, development needs, etc.).

Expertise at the technical level consists of ensuring that the MEI file generated during the workflow complies with the main standards of the format (i.e. it is syntactically valid) and that it preserves a consensual structure of XML elements, attributes and their values. The scalable level focuses more on the practicality of the workflow depending on the size of the corpus. In the age of Big Data,

it is essential for many research projects to use the most efficient automated methods to manage large numbers of files. However, it is not uncommon to encounter inefficiencies caused by workflows that are poorly suited to the task at hand. The ergonomic level focuses more on the human investment required to learn and use the tools.

The second part of the article is dedicated to the processes used to manipulate MEI files in order to enrich or modify them. It is less about comparing different workflows and more about presenting the most suitable tools and methods for various situations, whether they involve the header or the music section. The MEI ecosystem, in this respect, shows relatively little redundancy. This part will introduce the major tools used in MEI file manipulation and describe their advantages and potential for generalisation, or conversely, their use in more specific contexts. Once again, a section will be dedicated to notations other than standard Western common notation. The conclusion will highlight best practices and provide reflections on the presented workflows.

2. MEI workflows for conversion

2.1. *Verovio and MEI Garage web applications*

Using web applications to standardise or convert digital files is now a common process. But the files reserved for music publishing often escape this generality because the generation of the main formats used (MusicXML, MIDI, etc.) is most often derived from software (proprietary or non-proprietary), used locally and equipped with the most basic conversion functions. MEI is the exception that proves the rule. By its very nature, the format is independent from editing systems such as Sibelius, MuseScore or Dorico. This is why the need to use a conversion tool that is just as distinct as these software applications quickly becomes an essential condition for using MEI.

Web applications, widely supported by the MEI community, are available and well known to users, starting with the famous Verovio. Developed by Laurent Pugin, the Verovio website includes a range of tools: an SVG viewer, an editor and, among other things, a MusicXML to MEI converter (Pugin, Zitellini, and Roland 2014).³ Some of these features are also available on the command line or through JavaScript and Python libraries – these aspects will be covered in greater detail in the following workflows (section 2.5). While Verovio has quickly established itself in the musicological community due to its ability to efficiently convert and visualise scores, its popularity is also due to its integration into different web interfaces and environments. It has been implemented in several major databases, such as DME (the Digital Mozart Edition of the

3. *Verovio*, <https://www.verovio.org/index.xhtml>

Mozarteum), Measuring Polyphony (dir. Karen Desmond) and MODE (Marenzio Online Digital Edition).⁴

Another popular web application is MEI Garage, created by ViFE (Virtueller Forschungsverbund Edirom/Virtual Research Association Edirom).⁵ Adapted from OxGarage for TEI, MEI Garage is specially designed for converting and validating files. With a streamlined interface designed to simplify processes, this tool is sometimes the preferred choice of users looking for a fast solution for generating MEI files from a variety of formats. In fact, the application offers multiple conversions to or from MEI: Lilypond, MIDI, MusicXML, etc. Online conversion using forms to select input and output formats (following the same logic as the REST API discussed in section 2.5) is intuitive and rich in possibilities.

2.2. A few prerequisites for presenting workflows

To compare the different workflows that can be envisaged (although this study remains non-exhaustive), this paper proposes, at first, to focus on a simple method of generating an MEI file, namely its conversion from another format. Although various formats are mentioned for illustrative purposes, I mainly examine the export from MusicXML to MEI. This choice is guided by the fundamental role that MusicXML plays in the MEI environment. Since MusicXML is an interoperable format used by almost all music software, most MEI files are generated from it. Analysis of more varied and multidirectional conversions between Humdrum, Lilypond, MEI and MusicXML has already been undertaken, particularly with regard to the strictly musical aspects (Nápoles López, Vigliensoni, and Fujinaga 2019). Here, the focus will instead be on the subtle differences that can radically alter the interpretation and computational processing of the file.

The first prerequisite is that the source file is valid and well formed. In the case of XML files, there are many validators on the web that can be used to assess their quality. Files produced by music editing software encounter few problems of this kind. However, MEI is a semantic format, in the sense that all data must be rigorously integrated according to its ontological function. Indeed, just as an ontology structures and makes explicit the relationships between concepts and entities in a domain, MEI requires each musical element (metadata, note, measure, etc.) to be encoded according to its nature and precise role in the work. It is therefore necessary to limit as far as possible the “tinkering” with XML files that many music publishers engage in.⁶ For example, a piece of

4. *Mozarteum*, <https://dme.mozarteum.at/>; *Measuring Polyphony*, <https://measuringpolyphony.org/>; *MODE*, <https://marenzio.org/index.xhtml>

5. *MEI Garage*, <https://meigarage.edirom.de/>

6. Regarding the various points mentioned here, see the online workflow from the Musica2 consortium (Huma-Num), “Music Encoding Initiative from MusicXML”, available on the SSH Open Marketplace: <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/q2Z2Lo>.

metadata, such as the source of the edition, should not be in a field reserved for indications on musical staves (reserved for nuances, aesthetic indications, etc.). It is therefore important to make maximum use of the metadata forms available in music editing software, although the possibilities vary from case to case. The same applies to the choice of musical clefs, which must match the transposing instruments or voices (e.g. a tenor voice in the G-clef with *ottava bassa*). This avoids transposition problems during conversions.

Similarly, the layout of the score should not be based primarily on visual strategies that alter the XML structure. For example, in the case of early music, it is common practice to use an incipit, i.e. a false measure that is purely editorial to provide the original musical clefs or the first notes encountered in the sources. However, this practice, which originated in the paper tradition, no longer has any reason to exist in the context of a purely digital edition, as this same information can be rigorously encoded in a specific part of the MEI file (<incip>).⁷ The use of a false bar in a MusicXML file leads to a shift in the bar count and to various structural problems during conversion. It is worth noting that certain tools exist to clean and subsequently correct the generated MEI file if it is partially “altered”. Richard Freedman’s MEI Music Feature Correction is one of them.⁸ This tool, developed in Python and usable via the command line, requires a minimum level of technical knowledge to be used effectively. However, pre-cleaning the reference file before conversion remains the best practice.

While the various aspects mentioned so far are crucial, there are many other similar issues and situations. Most of these have recently been addressed as part of the GioQoso project (Foscarin, Rigaux, and Thion 2021). In addition, projects dealing with non-standard repertoires – such as mensural music or neumatic notation – often require specific encoding features provided by the official MEI customisations. These modules adapt the MEI framework to the graphic and semantic specificities of notational systems, enabling more accurate and consistent representations of early music corpora. Ignoring these customisations may lead to structural mismatches and loss of information during conversion or validation workflows – which is why they will be addressed in section 2.6. To sum up, it is essential to adopt the best practices of genuine digital editing, and not of “digitised” editing (Robinson 2002; Sahle 2016).

Before turning to these specialised modules in section 2.6, it is worth recalling that MEI also includes a core customisation known as MEI Basic. This profile defines a reduced subset of the MEI schema to streamline encoding practices for simpler use cases. MEI Basic includes the most essential elements and

7. Following the main conventions, XML elements are indicated by chevrons (e.g. <note>), attributes by an at symbol (e.g. @dur) and values by quotation marks (e.g. "brevis", "2").

8. https://github.com/RichardFreedman/mei_tools

attributes for representing common music notation, thereby reducing ambiguity and occasionally improving MEI integration into third-party systems in addition to certain lightweight conversion processes. However, in the context of research-driven projects that demand richer encodings, I focus here specifically on MEI Common Music Notation (MEI CMN) – i.e. modern Western musical notation, standardised since the 18th century – and the specialised modules it encompasses. These include digital scholarly editions, diplomatic transcriptions, or computational analyses (Rizo and Marsden 2019; Seipelt 2020), where the full expressive power of MEI, including its semantic depth and metadata granularity, becomes indispensable. In such cases, as we shall see, the simplicity of MEI Basic may not be sufficient to support the encoding needs, validation rules or data interoperability expected from scholarly digital workflows.

2.3. Comparison of Verovio and MEI Garage

Before comparing the results obtained with Verovio and MEI Garage, it is important to clarify the methodology used. The comparison was based on the conversion of a MusicXML file containing a monophonic piece exported from MuseScore (v.4.2).⁹ The file was submitted to MEI Garage via its online interface and converted with Verovio using the command-line tool. Both conversions used their respective tools' default settings. The resulting MEI files were analysed, with a focus on metadata structure and encoding consistency.

Converting files using online applications such as Verovio or MEI Garage is more a matter of spontaneous rather than regular use. The reason for this is that the web interface, which is always easy to use, offers file-by-file conversion and does not always allow fast processing of batches of data. Regardless of the tool, the production flow is virtually identical. As shown below (fig. 1),¹⁰ the data path from the generation of the source file is relatively long: (1) export of file into MusicXML or other suitable formats from software; (2) access to the web application; (3) loading of the source file into the web application; (4) online conversion; (5) downloading of the target file (MEI). The ergonomic level takes precedence over scalability: the applications are intuitive and do not require any special skills. This is why these tools play a key role in enhancing the value of MEI. However, the user is still heavily involved at every stage of the workflow, which means that the degree of ergonomics in terms of human investment and time-consuming activity needs to be nuanced.

9. The MusicXML file was manually enriched with missing minimal metadata, such as the source of the digital edition, following the official guidelines provided by MakeMusic. The different files are available on the following GitHub repository: <https://github.com/Musica2-WG1/MusicXML-to-MEI-conversion-resource/tree/main>.

10. The diagram is based on the international conventions for representing IT data flows.

Figure 1: Web application workflow diagram.

Not all tools are the same from a technical point of view. The comparison between Verovio and MEI Garage reveals structural differences that go beyond the surface. The most significant and relevant ones for this study are presented in table 1. Verovio generates MEI files that strictly follow the schema’s validation structure, including two declarations at the top of the file, enabling immediate XML validation. MEI Garage, by contrast, omits these but compensates with a richer and more descriptive `<meiHead>`. In the `<fileDesc>` section, Verovio distinguishes title elements using `<title>` and `<title type="subordinate">`, whereas MEI Garage uses a combination of `<title>` and `<identifier type="workNum">`. Even though the practice used in MEI Garage is scarcely documented in the MEI guidelines, Verovio’s approach appears preferable as it respects the controlled value "subordinate" for the `<title>` element.¹¹ In terms of syntax, MEI Garage surprisingly generates a few nesting problems in the XML structure. The nesting is imperfect and mixes header elements with others.

Table 1: Comparison of Verovio and MEI Garage.

Comparative aspect	MusicXML	MEI (Verovio)	MEI (MEI Garage)
XML Declarations			
Validation declarations	/	<code><?xml-model href="..."?></code> (2 lignes)	(No declaration)
<fileDesc>			
Title and subtitle (<code><titleStmnt></code>)	<code><work><work-number>+<work-title></code>	<code><fileDesc><titleStmnt><title>+<title type="subordinate"></code>	<code><fileDesc><titleStmnt><title><identifier type="workNum"></code>
Composer (<code><titleStmnt></code>)	<code><identification><creator type="composer"></code>	<code><respStmnt><persName role="composer"></code>	<code><composer><name role="composer"></code>
Encoding date (<code><pubStmnt></code>)	<code><encoding><encoding-date></code>	<code><pubStmnt><date isodate="2025-04-02" type="encoding-date"></code>	Self-closing tag : <code><pubStmnt/></code>
Copyright	<code><identification><rights></code>	<code><pubStmnt><availability><distributor></code>	Self-closing tag : <code><pubStmnt/></code>
Encoding date (<code><sourceDesc></code>)	/	/	<code><sourceDesc><source><annot><date></code>
Copyright (<code><sourceDesc></code>)	/	/	<code><sourceDesc><source><bibl><imprint><annot></code>
Title and subtitle (<code><sourceDesc></code>)	<code><work><work-number>+<work-title></code>	Absence of <code><sourceDesc></code>	<code><sourceDesc><source><bibl><title><identifier type="workNum"></code>
Composer (<code><sourceDesc></code>)	<code><identification><creator type="composer"></code>	Absence of <code><sourceDesc></code>	<code><sourceDesc><source><bibl><composer></code>
<encodingDesc>			
Conversion date	/	<code><applInfo><application isodate="2025-04-02T10:59:50"></code>	/
<revisionDesc>			
Conversion date	/	Absence of <code><revisionDesc></code>	<code><change><changeDesc>+<date isodate=" 2025-04-02"></code>
<workList>			
Title and subtitle	<code><work><work-number>+<work-title></code>	Absence of <code><workList></code>	<code><work><title><identifier type="workNum"></code>
Composer	<code><identification><creator type="composer"></code>	Absence of <code><workList></code>	<code><composer><composer><name role="composer"></code>
header (général)			
Attributes <code>xm:mid</code>		<code>xm:mid</code> on each element	Very few <code>xm:mid</code>
<music>			
Metadata layout	<code><credit><credit-type>+<credit-words></code>	<code><scoreDef><pglHead><rend></code>	/
Score definition	<code><attributes><divisions>+<key>+<time>+<clef></code>	<code><staffDef><label>+<instrDef>+<clef>+<keySig>+<meterSig></code>	<code><scoreDef key.sig="0" meter.count="6" meter.unit="8"><staffGrp><staffDef></code>
<code>xm:mid</code>	/	<code>xm:mid</code> on each element	<code>xm:mid</code> only in <code><note></code> and <code><measure></code>
MIDI values (@ppq, @dur.ppq)	/	In <code><staffDef></code> and <code><note></code>	/
Accidental	<code><note><accidental></code>	<code><note><accid accid="s"></code>	<code><note accid="s"></code>
Syllable position	<code><lyric><syllabic></code>	Always present with @wordpos	Sometimes missing

11. See listing 32 in the chapter “3.3.1 Title Statement” of the *MEI guidelines*, <https://music-encoding.org/guidelines/v5/content/metadata.html#headerTitleStatement>.

Composer information is encoded differently as well: Verovio uses `<respStmt><persName role="composer">`, while MEI Garage adopts `<composer><name role="composer">`. These choices reflect distinct editorial logics, both formally valid in MEI. However, both the MEI guidelines and general practice clearly favour the use of the `<respStmt>` and `<persName>` elements,¹² as they allow for explicit encoding of individual identities and their roles within the header.¹³ Notably, MEI Garage’s encoding here is redundant, as both `<composer>` and `@role` express the same information. The `<pubStmt>` element is auto-closed in MEI Garage (i.e., `<pubStmt/>`), while Verovio may include a full `<date>` or `<availability>` structure for copyright and encoding information. Again, Verovio adheres more closely to the MEI guideline conventions. MEI Garage, for its part, places this same information under `<sourceDesc>`, which is both unusual and incorrect. It is worth recalling that this section is primarily intended to describe the sources underlying the MEI edition.

MEI Garage includes a `<sourceDesc>` and a `<workList>`, both filled with minimal bibliographic metadata – elements that are missing in Verovio exports. Interestingly, in both cases, the bibliographic reference to the original source (`<encoding><source>` in MusicXML) is not preserved. The explanation is straightforward: few MusicXML files contain this field, as most score editing software does not provide a way to enter that metadata. The elements highlighted in red in table 1 are those whose placement in the header is debatable. This is the case in MEI Garage, which uses the `<sourceDesc>` section to indicate copyright or the encoding date.

At the musical level (`<music>`), both tools encode the same pitch and rhythmic information.¹⁴ However, Verovio adds `@dur . ppq` attributes (in `<note>`), intended for a MIDI format, and assigns `@xml:id` attributes to elements such as `<note>`, `<measure>` and `<beam>`, supporting cross-referencing and validation. MEI Garage uses these identifiers more sparingly. In the header,

12. “It is often desirable to mix primary and secondary intellectual responsibility information. Treating all intellectual roles the same way can allow literal transcription of existing responsibility statements and simplify programmatic processing. The following example demonstrates how a responsibility statement may be transcribed using interleaved `<resp>` and `<persName>` elements [...]”, see chapter “3.3.2 Responsibility Attribution” of the *MEI guidelines*, <https://music-encoding.org/guidelines/v5/content/metadata.html#headerrespstatement>.

13. `<name>` is reserved for any proper name to be encoded, regardless of questions of responsibility or personal identity. This is why, when used independently of `<respStmt>`, it is less relevant in MEI headers than the `<persName>` element, meanwhile modelled on the element of the same name in the Encoded Archival Description. With `<persName>`, responsibilities are most often indicated using the `@role` attribute.

14. It should be noted that the main differences in music encoding are more often to be found in the initial MusicXML. A useful resource for comparing different exports based on different tools is Klaus Rettinghaus et al., “MusicXML export comparison files (1.0).” [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8305206>

they are completely absent. Syllabic placement and accidentals are encoded similarly, though Verovio shows greater consistency in the use of the `@word-pos` attribute in lyrics.

In short, while MEI Garage leans toward editorial and bibliographic completeness, Verovio appears overall better suited to the manipulation, querying and long-term preservation of MEI files. This is largely due to its stricter adherence to the MEI guidelines and to XML validation practices. By systematically assigning `xml:id` attributes and respecting common vocabularies and syntax, Verovio facilitates machine-readability and reliable addressing of internal elements. These aspects are crucial for automated workflows, searchability and integration with digital libraries or research infrastructures. In this sense, Verovio's exports may offer greater sustainability and interoperability over time, particularly in contexts that rely on programmatic processing and standard-based data preservation. As the use of web applications is most often associated with a lack of automation in research projects, it is even more important for musicologists to choose the online converter that best meets their expectations for metadata completion.

2.4. Software and plug-ins: Sibelius and MuseScore

The accessibility of MEI conversion functions has improved considerably thanks to the development of music editing software capable of generating MEI files. These include both proprietary tools and open access applications. This increased accessibility is testament to the growing popularity of MEI and its adoption in various digital environments. Nevertheless, its integration into these software applications is not always initiated by the programmers themselves: it is often the result of community initiatives or the work of individual developers committed to the dissemination of this standard.

An example of this dynamic is the SibMEI plug-in, designed in part by Andrew Hankinson, Anna Plaksin and Klaus Rettinghaus, which allows users of the proprietary Sibelius software to export scores directly in MEI format, without the need for external tools.¹⁵ More recently, Andrew Hankinson also contributed to the development of a similar plug-in for MuseScore (MEI export), which is both open source and open access.¹⁶ Because of its accessibility, this software occupies a special place in the music notation landscape: MuseScore (now MuseScore Studio) is gradually taking its place as the symbolic free music notation interface that was missing from MEI, enabling its integration in an open-source environment. Since version MuseScore Studio 4.2, export to MEI has been directly integrated into the software, making conversion even easier.

15. *SibMEI* (GitHub repository), <https://github.com/music-encoding/sibmei>

16. *MEI Export* (GitHub repository), <https://github.com/rism-digital/musescore-mei>

For versions prior to 4.2, the conversion (from MusicXML to MEI) is performed via a Verovio web service. The plug-in is installed in the same way as any other MuseScore plug-in, and it is very well documented on the software's official website.¹⁷ This feature marks a desire to standardise the generation of MEI files using Verovio.

The use of plug-ins for conversion to MEI offers significant advantages in terms of ergonomics and efficiency. By incorporating the conversion steps directly into the host software interface, plug-ins centralise several steps in the conversion workflow (fig. 2), simplifying the process. This integration gives users the impression of a facilitated process and enables them to remain in a single, familiar environment, without having to switch between several applications. This is why, as part of its mission to promote the MEI format, the Musica2 Consortium in digital musicology (Huma-Num) is working hard to introduce these workflows to the musicology community.¹⁸ A tutorial published by Musica2 is available on the Social Sciences & Humanities (SSH) Open Marketplace and simultaneously presents two workflows, one of which uses the SibMEI plug-in.¹⁹

Figure 2: Software workflow diagram.

Being able to convert scores without leaving the music editing software not only improves the user experience but also ensures that the MEI files generated are consistent with everyone's editing habits. Plug-ins also take advantage of the host software's native functionalities, such as metadata management, annotations or complex notations. For example, MuseScore's metadata forms are relatively comprehensive and allow extensive metadata to be injected into the MSCX file (MuseScore's native format) and preserved during MEI conversion. Moreover,

17. MuseScore, <https://musescore.org/en/project/mei-export>

18. Musica2 Consortium, <https://musica.hypotheses.org/>

19. *Supra* n. 6.

these simple workflows are not always limited to “file-by-file” export. The SibMEI plug-in allows the easy export of folder contents (Sibelius or MusicXML files). In MuseScore, it is technically possible to export several files at once using the Batch Convert plug-in, but this requires more maintenance and development of MEI export in recent versions of the software.

However, it should be noted that MEI files exported from MuseScore, including the native export function introduced in version 4.2, conform to the MEI Basic schema (Kijas et al. 2024). As such, they are limited to a core set of MEI elements and may require further enrichment or transformation for research contexts involving specialised modules or extended metadata structures.²⁰ For its part, the SibMEI plug-in provides a suitable structure, focusing on a set of metadata extracted directly from the Sibelius file. These include the title and subtitle (<title>), the names of contributors such as the composer, lyricist or arranger (<composer>, <lyricist>, <arranger>), a free-text note (<annot>) for additional information and the copyright. This metadata is structured both within <fileDesc> (via <titleStmt> and <pubStmt>) and within <workList>, which is significant for producing more complete and rigorous headers. As a result, MEI files converted from Sibelius tend to be richer in metadata (provided this information is properly filled in via the software’s form) than those exported from MuseScore.

It should also be noted that plug-ins which depend on a web service, such as MuseScore’s MEI Export (for versions prior to 4.2), do not guarantee constant use, particularly in the event of an unstable or inaccessible internet connection. The potential obstacles in this case are the same as for web applications. Moreover, conversion issues are not uncommon, as plug-ins require maintenance just like third-party services, which can lead to additional correction time.

2.5. Programmatic conversion and manipulation use case

The tools and methods presented in this section are suitable for automating research projects. Automation is not always part of an overall programming approach, despite the obvious close link. It can be considered as an optimisation strategy aimed at improving the efficiency of a project while reducing the

20. “Other limitations are bound to MuseScore’s design and to the difference between its internal data structure and the MEI model. For instance, the metadata export is limited to about a dozen meta-fields that are available by default in MuseScore. Another limitation is related to the handling of IDs. Since IDs are a key concept in MEI, and are extensively used in many MEI-based applications, clarifying, documenting and potentially improving their handling in the MuseScore implementation will be an important task in the future.”, Kijas et al. 2024. “MEI-basic Support in MuseScore 4.2” *Music Encoding Conference 2024*. Denton. <https://doi.org/10.17613/ccmr-yv05>

repetitive tasks performed by humans. In the field of digital musicology, the use of task automation fluctuates significantly depending on the project, the individual and the laboratory. This variability is mainly linked to individual skills and the technical knowledge available. Indeed, the IT training of musicologists and, more broadly, of researchers in the humanities and social sciences is still often sketchy. This section therefore continues its didactic approach, setting out in a simple and accessible way various workflows for using command-line MEI tools, APIs and scripts.

The MEI ecosystem includes a variety of programmatic methods. The MEI Garage EGE Webservice is a first example.²¹ This is a service for manipulating and validating MEI files and other text and music data formats. Like all REST APIs, this interface enables interaction with the web application via HTTP requests. These can then be accessed directly via a browser. However, the main advantage lies in the generation of request URLs in order to automate the functions available. This method can be done via command lines or integrated directly into programming scripts. This is useful for large-scale manipulation of MEI files or for facilitating their validation. The same functionalities of the web application are accessible via the API. In particular, the “Conversion” section enables MEI files to be converted to other document formats or upgraded to more recent versions. All formats can be consulted via the API (GET function) using the following URL: <https://meigarage.edirom.de/ege-webservice/Conversions>. This request instantly returns the types of input and output formats available. Conversion is carried out using the POST function associated with the generic URL: `/ege-webservice/Conversions/{input-document-type}/{output-document-type}`. The labels for “input-document-type” and “output-document-type” are determined from the list of supported conversion formats.

While an API can be useful for automating tasks, it is still dependent on access to servers and the state of the internet connection. The smooth running of the workflow depends largely on its availability and stability. MEI Garage can be installed locally, using a Docker image, and used from an internal network (localhost:8080).²² But there are other tools and methods that are truly local. Their functionalities offer greater control and flexibility, particularly useful when processing large datasets. Verovio, like MuseScore, can be used on the command line to convert batches of MEI files in a very short time. Installation is quick and well documented on the official website.²³ For example, the following command-line script (in a Unix terminal) converts

21. MEI Garage API, <https://meigarage.edirom.de/ege-webservice/>

22. See MEI Garage (GitHub repository), <https://github.com/Edirom/MEIGarage>

23. See Verovio, <https://book.verovio.org/installing-or-building-from-sources/command-line.html>

all the files in the directory opened via the terminal with the XML extension (for MusicXML) to MEI:

```
for file in *.xml; do
verovio -f musicxml -t mei -o "${file%.xml}.mei" "$file"
done
```

The way in which a command line is written is much the same as for the other tools presented so far, although the formats and conversion directions are different. While Verovio offers SVG projection and other formats, many other scripts with sometimes explicit names, such as `mei2hum`, allow conversion of MEI files to Humdrum or to Lilypond. Once again, all the functions and their shortcuts are described in detail on GitHub pages.²⁴ The diversity of output formats also suggests that the MEI is now capable of interacting with a wide range of file types and thus of incorporating complex and heterogeneous musicological research environments.

Within the MEI ecosystem, one final piece of software stands out as being very practical and particularly user-friendly. This is Meico, a program developed by Axel Berndt that can be installed and used locally to validate and convert MEI files into several formats.²⁵ The software version is an excellent initiative for promoting the use of the format using an intuitive interface. Meico proposes representing the files generated in a virtual two-dimensional plan and linking them like a graph. Users can immediately follow the various file conversion flows and explore their potential, to MSM (Musica Sequence Markup) or to vector data for pitches. The heuristic value of this tool is further enhanced by its support for the Music Performance Markup (MPM) format, which enables a precise description of how a music piece is performed. It also facilitates the application of XSLT sheets for file conversion. Each sheet can be integrated into the interface to transform a file. This is a welcome feature, as MEI's GitHub directory offers a set of XSLT sheets for converting to or from various formats.²⁶

Integrating these same tools into code provides even greater flexibility. Development libraries and modules for Python (e.g. Verovio) or JavaScript (e.g. Verovio, Meico) make it easy to integrate the automation of conversions, exports and validation of MEI files into larger workflows. For instance, using the Verovio Python module for conversion can more broadly integrate a script capable of sorting the MusicXML files to be exported according to their metadata. Below (table 2) is an example of a Python script which, in a folder containing hundreds of scores, retrieves only those MusicXML files whose

24. MEILER, <https://github.com/craigsapp/humlib>; <https://github.com/rettinghaus/MEILER>

25. Meico (GitHub repository), <https://github.com/cemfi/meico>

26. MEI tools (GitHub repository), <https://github.com/music-encoding/encoding-tools>

composer is Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart and exports them as MEI files into a different folder.²⁷

Table 2: Python code example for conversion to MEI based on metadata.

```
import verovio
import xml.etree.ElementTree as ET
import os

def check_composer_name(xml_file_path):
    tree = ET.parse(xml_file_path)
    root = tree.getroot()
    for creator in root.findall("./creator"):
        if creator.attrib.get('type') == 'composer' and 'Mozart'
in creator.text:
            return True
    return False

def convert_to_mei(xml_file_path, output_folder):
    if check_composer_name(xml_file_path):
        tk = verovio.toolkit()
        tk.loadFile(xml_file_path)
        base_name = os.path.basename(xml_file_path)
        mei_file_path = os.path.join(output_folder, base_name.replace('.
xml', '.mei'))
        mei_data = tk.getMEI()
        with open(mei_file_path, 'w', encoding='utf-8') as mei_file:
            mei_file.write(mei_data)

input_folder = "Path/to/input/folder"# here, add an input folder
output_folder = "Path/to/ouput/folder"# here, add an output folder
os.makedirs(output_folder, exist_ok=True)

for file_name in os.listdir(input_folder):
    if file_name.endswith(".xml"):
        xml_file_path = os.path.join(input_folder, file_name)
        convert_to_mei(xml_file_path, output_folder)
```

This simple code effectively reduces some of the steps in the web application workflows (fig. 1) and, as a result, considerably improves the generation of MEI files (fig. 3). It also removes many human interventions while offering the possibility of properly integrating other automated parts of a more sophisticated generation chain – in this case, the selection of files to be converted based on metadata (the identity of the composer in the XML line:

27. The corresponding Python script is available at: <https://github.com/Musica2-WG1/MusicXML-to-MEI-conversion-resource/tree/main>.

`<creator type="composer">Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart</creator>`). Situations of this type are numerous in research projects and can be resolved simply by a programmatic approach.

Figure 3: Programmatic workflow diagram.

Of course, scripts can be intimidating for musicologists who are unfamiliar with programming or who are not used to working with a code editor or a terminal. While programming remains a specific skill, there are accessible ways to become self-taught or productive. On the one hand, there are “no-code” tools that allow users to edit short scripts for basic tasks or even generate them from written instructions (prompt). While no-code tools may raise fundamental questions about the development of IT professions, it has the merit of making programming more accessible and therefore more widely used. It can even sometimes offer unexpected alternatives, not least through artificial intelligence specialising in data generation. Although deep learning models for language generation are not, strictly speaking, dedicated to computer code, the potential remains huge. This is the case with GPT-4 (OpenAI) in particular, which can write a minimal MEI file after being prompted to provide certain metadata and musical elements (note, rhythm, etc.).

On the other hand, it is also possible to draw inspiration from projects hosted in open directories such as GitHub. The very philosophy of the platform encourages the reuse of shared code in a variety of contexts. The code proposed above can also be quickly adapted to other situations with minor modifications. The question of training is therefore linked to the question of available teaching resources. According to *The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity*, researchers have a duty to document and share the technical support for their own research as effectively as possible.²⁸ Today, every digital project should

28. “Researchers, research institutions, and organisations ensure that access to data is as open as possible, as closed as necessary, and where appropriate in line with the FAIR Principles (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) for data management.” and “Researchers, research institutions, and organisations are transparent about how to

develop a rigorous educational aspect, not just for the public, but above all for the researchers themselves. This is why the Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud offers so many didactic resources and why funding programmes dedicated to advancing open science, such as the recent OSCARS open calls, place a strong emphasis on developing educational materials alongside technical and technological innovations.²⁹ Moreover, such initiatives are supported by established infrastructures in the humanities and social sciences, such as DARIAH or CLARIN. The pedagogical contribution to musicology has proved its worth in recent years, most recently in France through Huma-Num and its Musica2 Consortium.

2.6. Conversion beyond common music notation

The growing popularity of MEI has given rise to a diversity of workflows adapted to different music notation tools, free or proprietary, with the intention of facilitating the editorial chain or shortening the process by making the work steps more ergonomic. Nevertheless, this diversity is not only the result of user preferences. It also responds to the constraints posed by the divergent nature of encoded corpora, which are sometimes of ethnographic origin and markedly different from Western popular or scholarly practices (Martin de Guise 2013; Leblond Martin, 2016; Zitellini and Pugin 2016). Early music repertoires also present challenges and are not always supported by common editing software (Stinson and Stoessel 2014). Their notations, often incompatible with modern standards, require specialised formats capable of interpreting their rhythmic, symbolic or semantic structures. MEI, in this regard, proves to be a particularly practical output format. However, the workflows to achieve this are still rare and little known. This may seem paradoxical given the innovations in MEI integration of these notations, particularly through the modular structuring offered by the format. Among these, for example, the Mensural module allows the definition of characteristics specific to measured notation from the *ars antiqua* (13th century), while the Neumes module handles the structures of early neumatic notations, mainly for plainchant.

From a technical standpoint, each module corresponds to an XML namespace defined within the MEI schema and activated depending on the project's requirements. This modularity keeps MEI lightweight while ensuring the syntactic and semantic validation of encoded files according to the type of notation in use. It also offers future extensibility, enabling additional or restricted elements and attributes tailored to specific repertoires without compromising the overall

access and gain permission to use data, metadata, protocols, code, software, and other research materials.”, ALLEA - All European Academies. 2017. *The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity: Revised Edition*. <https://allea.org/code-of-conduct/>

29. Concerning the OSCARS open calls, see <https://oscars-project.eu/open-calls>.

schema coherence.³⁰ Some projects and initiatives have emerged to support efficient MEI conversion or generation, considering the specific features of each notation system as much as possible.

For mensural notation, one of the most functional projects in this area is *MEI_Translator*,³¹ developed as part of the Measuring Polyphony project led by Karen Desmond.³² This Python tool, used via command lines, enables automatic conversion of MEI files encoded in modern notation (CMN) into mensural notation, relying on transcription rules based on note duration and mensuration. It implements advanced conversion features, allowing adaptation to the subtle nuances of notation often implicit in repertoires from the *ars antiqua*, *ars nova*, and Renaissance white mensural notation. The workflow used in the project has proven effective for generating mensural MEI from MEI CMN. Most files were initially encoded using Sibelius, then exported to MEI (via SibMEI) and finally converted to MEI Mensural using *MEI_Translator*. Due to the complexity of the notation, the resulting MEI files may require refinement and correction to ensure proper encoding of mensural features not easily inferred from common notation. This tool, which is positioned downstream from a music editor such as Sibelius or MuseScore, therefore offers a simple and user-friendly alternative (with relatively easy installation) for data conversion. Measuring Polyphony also includes a symbolic editor, which will be discussed later.

More recently, Verovio has opened new possibilities for the conversion of mensural MEI. Since version 4.5, Verovio supports the new input format CMME (Computerised Mensural Music Editing), originally developed by Theodor Dumitrescu and Marnix van Berchum in the early 2000s (Dumitrescu 2001).³³ This XML schema, which originally came with its own editing interface, aimed to provide a dedicated tool for mensural repertoire. It allowed diplomatic digital transcription of fourteenth and fifteenth-century sources through integration of many graphical and stylistic conventions from mensural notation. Over time, the editor interface became obsolete, working only on outdated systems due to the deprecation of Java support.³⁴ Nevertheless, the CMME XML schema retains strong encoding capabilities, preserving many notated pieces created over the years. In 2024, the Cluster 6 Biblissima+ initiative³⁵ organised a hackathon to gather specialists and develop a conversion tool. This tool was integrated into Verovio and enhanced with convenient command-line features. Not only is it now possible to retain the original mensural notation of CMME files (CMME

30. See the addition of elements related to early notations introduced in MEI version 5.

31. *CMN-MEI to Mensural MEI Translator*, https://github.com/DDMAL/CMN-MEI_to_MensuralMEI_Translator

32. *Measuring Polyphony*, <https://measuringpolyphony.org/>

33. *CMME*, <https://www.cmme.org/>

34. *CMME editor*, <https://github.com/tdumitrescu/cmme-editor/tree/master>

35. *Biblissima+ Cluster 6*, <https://projet.biblissima.fr/fr/projet/clusters-biblissima/cluster-6>

to MEI Mensural), but conversion to modern notation (MEI Mensural to MEI CMN) is also supported. In this way, the sustainability of the CMME format is now ensured through Verovio. This data can persist within MEI, offering a good example of a FAIR-compliant solution within the digital musicology landscape.

A similar initiative also emerged following the obsolescence of the Scribe software, which was once highly valued for encoding medieval music notation. In this context, John Stinson and Jason Stoessel viewed MEI as a sustainable solution for preserving scores produced with Scribe: “The Music Encoding Initiative (MEI) emerged as an XML standard currently most suited to preserving Scribe’s valuable data and to making it available to a wider audience of specialist and generalist users. Of the non-proprietary standards useful for linked open data, only MEI has inbuilt support for chant (MEI Neumes) and mensural notation.” (Stinson and Stoessel 2014, 614). This intention gave rise to the C++ program Scribe2NeoScribe, which takes Scribe files as input and converts them into MEI.³⁶

Unlike measured music, whose rhythmic values can be arithmetically preserved in any XML specification, neume notations are poorly suited to this kind of export. This is why most dedicated software (Gregorio, Gregedit, etc.) is designed mainly for PDF or image dissemination. Therefore, the automatic generation of MEI files containing neume notation occasionally relies on optical music recognition tools (Helsen et al. 2014) – the manual encoding of this type of notation, using the Neon editor as an example, will be addressed later in section 3.3. Due to its semantic richness, MEI is increasingly being integrated into automatic music recognition pipelines, particularly the most advanced or experimental ones (Stoessel, Collins, and Bolland 2020). Nevertheless, conversion remains a delicate and rather uncommon process within the scope of the MEI Neumes module. It is, however, possible to convert a GABC file into MEI Neumes using dedicated scripts in the command line. The Python script GABCtoMEI (as part of Echoes From the Past project) automates this process.³⁷ Created by Martha E. Thomae and Elsa De Luca, it requires a source file in text format and produces an MEI file following the Neumes module. The user can also specify the desired notation type between square and Aquitanian. Given the popularity of the GABC format for the plainchant, this tool proves especially practical for generating MEI files that preserve the graphical and semantic characteristics of neumatic notations.

The situation is different for tablature, for which numerous formats and tools already exist. Among the most popular formats are jtxml (Fandango), ft3 (Fronimo) and tab (developed by Wayne Cripps). The musicological perspective

36. *Scribe2NeoScribe*, <https://github.com/jjstoessel/Scribe2NeoScribe>

37. *GABCtoMEI*, <https://github.com/ECHOES-from-the-Past/GABCtoMEI>

on the specific needs of tablature formats has even extended beyond MEI, with the development of the TabCode format by Tim Crawford (Wiering, Crawford, and Lewis 2005). As a result, the abundance of formats has led to a frequent need for data conversion. Therefore, for the MEI tablature module, some conversion systems do exist, such as Luteconv WebUI (as part of the E-LAUTE project).³⁸ This useful web application allows users to input a source file in various formats (ABC, MusicXML, tab, etc.) and export it to multiple formats, including MEI Tablature. Input parameters allow the user to specify the type of tablature (French, German, etc.). It is also possible to install LuteConv and use it via the command line, thereby unlocking greater potential for batch processing, but only on Linux systems. This initiative effectively serves as a bridge between widely used editorial formats and those specific to tablature. However, some data may not be preserved, depending on the different output formats.

These various initiatives demonstrate both the flexibility and modularity of MEI when it comes to accommodating early and non-standard music notations. Whether derived from mensural, neumatic, or tablature traditions, each repertoire presents unique challenges that call for tailored tools and workflows. While the overall number of fully automated solutions remains limited, the tools highlighted above offer concrete examples of successful conversions, from both legacy and modern editorial formats. Table 3 provides a summary of the main conversion workflows discussed, detailing the input formats, the tools employed, and the MEI modules or output types generated in each case.

Table 3: Summary table of the MEI conversion discussed for early notations.

Input format	Tool used	Output MEI module
MEI CMN	MEI-Translator	MEI Mensural
CMME	Verovio	MEI Mensural
MEI Mensural	Verovio	MEI CMN
Neu (Scribe)	Scribe2NeoScribe	MEI-Compliant XML (Mensural and Neumes)
GABC	GABCtoMEI	MEI Neumes
Jtxml, Ft3, MusicXML, Tab, Tc	Luteconv	MEI Tablature

Looking ahead, the same modular and extensible nature of MEI holds great promise for the encoding of non-Western and ethnomusicological notations. Although such repertoires are not yet formally supported within the current MEI modules, their growing representation in digital musicology underscores the need for future developments that reflect greater diversity in musical notation systems.

38. *Luteconv*, <https://github.com/LukeEmmet/luteconv/tree/master>; <https://luteconv.mdw.ac.at/>

3. MEI-based music editing workflows

3.1. Enriching MEI headers

The preservation and transmission of metadata between music notation software and MEI remains a major issue. As we have seen before, although MusicXML has become the *de facto* intermediary format for many MEI generation workflows, its capacity to retain rich and structured metadata is limited and highly dependent on the software used to export it. Metadata fields may be incomplete, misplaced or simply discarded during conversion. These inconsistencies directly impact the quality of the MEI files generated from MusicXML sources and may necessitate manual corrections or the use of complementary tools to reintroduce lost information.

Third-party applications allow MEI headers to be filled in using forms. This is the case with MerMEId (Metadata Editor and Repository for MEI Data), produced by the Danish Centre for Music Editing (Henny-Krahmer and Stadler 2022). MerMEId offers a user-friendly graphical interface that allows the structured input of metadata, strictly following MEI guidelines, without the need to manipulate XML code directly.³⁹ Although convenient and suitable for detailed manual entry, MerMEId does not support batch processing. Each MEI file must be edited individually, which significantly increases the workflow chain when dealing with large corpora. This lack of automatisation can be detrimental to the timetable of a research project, especially those requiring the insertion of metadata into dozens or hundreds of files.

Another recent Python program (`mei_metadata_processor.py`), developed by Richard Freedman, allows metadata to be injected into an MEI header from a spreadsheet.⁴⁰ This tool is particularly useful for projects that rely on a database containing analytical, historical or editorial metadata. Moreover, the metadata encoding strictly follows the MEI guidelines. While the tool can be used via the command line, it can also be run through a Jupyter Notebook. Technically, the script operates by processing a folder of MEI files and generating updated files into a specified output directory. Metadata is supplied in the form of a list of dictionaries imported from a CSV file. The tool thus enables a simple, structured and automated collection of MEI headers, highly useful for batch processing in large-scale music encoding projects.

39. *MerMeid*, <https://mermeid.edirom.de/about.html>; <https://github.com/Edirom/MerMEId>. For a quick presentation, see Crandell, Adam. 2015. "Review of *MerMEId: Metadata Editor and Repository for MEI Data*, by The National Library, Danish Centre for Music Publication." *Notes* 71 (3): 543-44. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1353/not.2015.0037>

40. *Mei tools*, https://github.com/RichardFreedman/mei_tools

3.2. Music editing, enhancement, and enrichment

The MEI ecosystem also includes tools that focus more specifically on music editing. During MEI training workshops, it is not uncommon to hear concerns about the lack of ergonomic, user-friendly tools for directly handling the symbolic content (i.e. the `<music>` section) of MEI files. For many users, especially those familiar with notation software such as Sibelius or Dorico, it can be frustrating to realise that no fully-featured score editor currently supports MEI as a native format. This limitation underscores a persistent gap in the MEI ecosystem, where symbolic editing is still often mediated through intermediate formats like MusicXML.

MEISE (MEI Score Editor), developed under the direction of DARIAH-DE, aimed to provide an intuitive online interface for editing MEI files. While the tool is still accessible online in its 2016 beta version,⁴¹ it can no longer be installed on recent operating systems, and its interactive features appear to be largely non-functional. Despite being a pioneering initiative in the field of digital musicology, MEISE illustrates the challenges of sustainability faced by specialised editorial environments, particularly when long-term maintenance is lacking or when community support is insufficient. That said, MEISE undoubtedly paved the way for later initiatives by highlighting the need for accessible and ergonomic environments for MEI editing. Its core ambition – to model the architecture of MEI files through an easy-to-use interface – remains highly relevant and inspiring for future developments in the field.

The idea of an interface that bridges the gap between a code editor and a music notation editor remains central within the MEI ecosystem. Among the tools that address this challenge is the Verovio Editor, integrated into the broader Verovio toolset. It is a browser-based tool combining a real-time XML code editor with an interactive musical score renderer (Verovio viewer). It allows users to visualise and modify MEI files simultaneously, making it suitable for last-minute corrections to MEI files without needing a separate rendering engine. Faced with the need to move toward an even more ergonomic and functional tool, a similar trajectory can be observed in the case of Mei-Friend.⁴² Initially developed as a plug-in for the Atom editor, it facilitated real-time rendering and basic manipulation of MEI content directly within the XML environment. The end of Atom’s development in 2022 posed a serious threat to the usability of the Mei-Friend plug-in. That was without counting on the creation of a dedicated web application, a “last-mile editor”. This web-based version preserves the original philosophy of the plug-in while expanding its accessibility, especially for non-programmers. It allows users to edit MEI files,

41. MEISE, <https://meise.de.dariah.eu/>

42. Mei-Friend, <https://mei-friend.mdw.ac.at/>

visualise them with Verovio and perform conversions – making it a valuable educational and editorial tool, despite certain limitations in batch processing.

The primary aim of Mei-Friend is to equip the musicological community with a centralised and flexible editing environment in which to streamline the handling and manipulation of MEI files. The simultaneous display of external images (handwritten sources, digitised editions, etc.), the MEI code and the SVG projection allows unparalleled navigation in the richness of the format. The numerous keyboard shortcuts and dynamic interaction with Verovio’s visualisation are extremely practical for inserting semantic data (trill, glissando, fermata, etc.) that can be tedious to encode manually. Mei-Friend also offers the same conversion possibilities as Verovio. Its features aim to enhance the semantic scope of MEI through an intuitive and straightforward annotation management system. In addition, the simplified integration of external identifiers and URIs from the web and the possibility of exporting annotations as RDF effectively positions the MEI file within the broader context of linked open data. It is an essential tool for any MEI editor or encoder, regardless of their level of technical proficiency.

Another major step forward in the democratisation of MEI editing is the increasing integration of MEI export features into MuseScore, an open-source notation software. Although MuseScore does not natively work with MEI (its format being a compressed MusicXML), it would be remiss not to mention the significance of this software in the MEI editing workflow. MuseScore plays a crucial role as an upstream editor in the pipeline. In many ways, it is becoming the symbolic front-end for MEI: a free and widely used environment where symbolic notation is created, edited, exported or imported in MEI format. MEI export is included in MuseScore (version 4.2 and later) and requires no additional plug-ins or web service. This stands in contrast to earlier versions, where export was routed through a remote Verovio-based web service, raising concerns about stability. With native support now embedded, MuseScore positions itself as the most accessible MEI-compatible editing environment, especially for scholars and musicians working outside of a strictly technical or programmatic context.

Nevertheless, the usefulness and efficiency of MuseScore in the MEI editing and enrichment chain must be qualified. MuseScore remains, above all, a music notation editor, not an XML code editor. As such, any corrections made using it – benefiting from MuseScore’s built-in features and overall user-friendliness – will largely be superficial. MuseScore’s metadata form offers only a slight improvement in completeness compared to similar tools, and the integration of many semantic tags, annotations and other advanced MEI structures is not possible through its interface. This limitation is inherent to its current implementation of MEI export, which is based on the MEI Basic schema. Therefore,

it would be misleading to compare MuseScore to a tool like Mei-Friend, even though it undeniably contributes to the wider adoption of MEI and its integration into broader, more popular workflows.

Together, these examples reflect both the fragility and adaptability of the MEI ecosystem. Tools emerge, disappear or evolve, and the community's ability to respond to infrastructural shifts – as with Mei-Friend's migration or MuseScore's integration – remains one of MEI's greatest strengths.

3.3. Tools and methods for early music notation

The manipulation of MEI files in the context of early music currently relies on a heterogeneous ecosystem of tools, with varying levels of support depending on the type of notation. This section presents the most specialised workflows – where available – for the semantic and symbolic manipulation of the MEI modules Mensural, Neumes and Tablature.

In principle, the visualisation of MEI files is handled by Verovio, which supports many features of these three notations. For the Mensural and Tablature modules, the limitations of the system are generally marginal – some specific difficulties will be discussed below. Thus, it is perfectly feasible to visualise these types of MEI files without major issues, as long as the encoded scores remain within a relatively “conventional” framework. For example, Verovio provides various command-line options dedicated to rendering mensural notation. These options mainly concern editorial conventions (such as rendering ligatures as brackets, controlling the shape of ligatures, selecting the base rhythmic value, automatic layering of voices, etc.).

However, for the Neume module, visualisation mainly focuses on square notation and still poses various difficulties in producing coherent and well-represented groupings of neumes. It is clear that the absence of musical measures makes the distribution of figures across staves more complex, as the temporal organisation of notes is now governed by the sequence of syllables rather than by a properly musical logic. This issue becomes even more pronounced with older neumatic notations and with adiaستمatic forms (i.e. without relative pitch). The diversity of regional graphic traditions coupled with the absence of a reference pitch system make symbolic display quite challenging. In most cases, these shortcomings are addressed at the research project level by recruiting a computer scientist to build a customised rendering system. This is notably the case with the recent Carmina Burana Online project led by Christelle Cazaux (Schola Cantorum Basiliensis), which aims to produce a digital edition of the famous Codex Buranus.

These challenges directly affect the capabilities of user-friendly editors. Although it is indeed possible to visualise MEI files using mensural figures, tablature or

neumes in tools like Mei-Friend, their ergonomic manipulation will remain more limited compared to CMN files. Only basic functionalities are retained. In this context, manipulation often requires editing the XML code directly, which is why the idea of editors specifically dedicated to these notations has been the focus of several development efforts. The Measuring Polyphony project, led by Karen Desmond, has notably produced the Measuring Polyphony Music Editor (funded by the National Endowment for the Humanities).⁴³ This symbolic interface builds on a tailored adaptation of Verovio, allowing users to edit and visualise mensural MEI files interactively, in direct connection with digitised sources via the IIF protocol (Desmond and Kijas 2021).⁴⁴ The symbolic editor enables the encoding of many features of medieval and Renaissance polyphony, from the thirteenth to the sixteenth centuries. It can also be used locally to support different needs outside the original project, making it a valuable tool for manipulating or editing mensural MEI files.

A similar project for neume notation is Neon (Neume Editor ONline), developed within the Distributed Digital Music Archives and Libraries Lab in Montreal (Burlet et al. 2012).⁴⁵ The editor offers a symbolic interface for quickly encoding liturgical sources in square notation in MEI. The system, built in JavaScript, is based on Verovio. It is currently the most user-friendly and straightforward web application available for editing this type of notation from primary sources. It can also be used locally. However, since the visual layout of neumes on the page relies on a specific adaptation of Verovio, the MEI files generated may not always render with the same quality in third-party systems like Mei-Friend or other implementations of Verovio. Managing staff breaks and the absolute positioning of musical figures may cause issues.

It is important to note that for other highly specific notations – whether Western or from ethnographic traditions not yet formally modelled in MEI – additional development is still required. Some initiatives have emerged to meet these particular needs. One such example is the SubtiliorEditor program (as part of a partnership between Cluster 6 Biblissima+ and the Musica2 Consortium), developed for music written in the style of the *ars subtilior* (MEI Mensural). This program allows for the graphic and semantic encoding of complex figures (such as *semibreves caudatae*) using a simplified vocabulary while automatically generating MEI files that conform to the mensural model. Because it lacks a symbolic interface, the Python script is intended for command-line use. Such tools, as is often the case for applications targeting marginal or historically less common notational systems, are generally aimed at users with prior experience in automated workflows and MEI-based encoding practices.

43. *Measuring Polyphony Editor*, https://github.com/MeasuringPolyphony/mp_editor

44. For the web application in Measuring Polyphony, <https://editor.measuringpolyphony.org/#/>

45. *Neon*, <https://ddmal.ca/software/neon/>; <https://github.com/DDMAL/Neon>

4. Conclusion and prospects

There are undoubtedly other methods or tools for handling MEI files, but this study has enabled us to look at several of them and show the range of workflows and tools available. Their diversity demonstrates the growing maturity and adaptability of the MEI ecosystem. From simple web applications to more advanced programmatic pipelines, each approach offers specific advantages depending on the user's needs, expertise and the type of repertoire involved.

Let us begin by surveying the converters available for common music notation (CMN) independently of notation software. Among them, Verovio stands out for its ability to combine rigorous syntax with commendable compliance with the MEI guidelines. However, a more in-depth assessment of its performance would be beneficial, particularly by testing alternative input formats to MusicXML, in order to evaluate its handling of metadata and other intricacies specific to MEI.

As for historical notations, which fall outside the scope of MusicXML standards, there are, fortunately, solutions (albeit of uneven quality) that allow for MEI representation. Several strategies are available to users: converting an MEI CMN file into MEI Mensural or turning to formats more suited to historical notation systems (NeoScribe, CMME, GABC, Tab, etc.). That said, the specialisation of these formats often comes with added complexity for users less familiar with digital tools, especially since they generally require local installation and command-line usage. While such constraints may discourage those seeking ease of use, they remain the most effective path to fully harnessing the power of these tools.

The core issue lies in the modalities of using MEI generation tools. Verovio, widely acclaimed in the MEI ecosystem, owes its popularity as much to its technical reliability as to its versatility – including its integration into MuseScore. While software applications like MuseScore offer excellent usability, their export capabilities remain limited. These limitations are due as much to the supported export standards (e.g. MEI Basic for MuseScore) as to the internal restrictions of the software itself, particularly concerning metadata management. In this respect, SibMEI allows for richer MEI headers than MuseScore, making it a more robust option, although its proprietary nature raises ethical and economic concerns, especially in light of the FAIR principles and the financial constraints of research institutions.

Moreover, the human effort required to operate these systems is often underestimated. Their apparent simplicity conceals limitations when working at scale. MuseScore is well suited for occasional editing but lacks compatibility with batch processing, which hinders large-scale projects. Sibelius, on the

other hand, is better equipped for batch processing, making it more efficient for major research projects. Nevertheless, this efficiency does not automatically translate into better semantic encoding, which remains essential in a scholarly context.

The same limitations apply to web-based applications, whose user-friendly interfaces, while ideal for quick adoption, limit automation capabilities. Conversely, local command-line tools and programming libraries make it possible to exploit the full potential of MEI converters, especially within automated environments. Projects involving large corpora naturally favour such approaches, particularly when combined with data collection or analytical workflows.

In research contexts that require richly annotated MEI files, no tool is universally optimal. Some workflows, however, prove more effective than others. As previously noted, starting from a MusicXML file gives little hope of preserving a substantial amount of metadata through conversion. Post-conversion enrichment – through Verovio, for example – is therefore preferable. This can be achieved manually via forms or more efficiently through automated injection from spreadsheets (as demonstrated by Richard Freedman). The latter solution streamlines data updates and optimises the overall editorial workflow – a key advantage for database-driven projects.

For more targeted interventions on the files, such as corrections or enhancements within the `<music>` section, symbolic interfaces with code editors are the most appropriate. These tools are natively compatible with MEI and avoid the intermediate conversions required by MuseScore or Sibelius, which must reformat files to their proprietary schemas. In this respect, Mei-Friend is among the most relevant tools. Although its functions apply primarily to MEI CMN, it remains indispensable for refining score encoding and rendering. Beyond common Western notation, there are also open-source interfaces offering specific functionalities that are particularly valuable in many research projects. These tools would benefit from increased development and visibility.

Finally, the automation of editorial practices remains a significant technical challenge. While digital editing is steadily advancing, the design of genuinely automated workflows tailored to the demands of research remains an evolving field. It is worth recalling that editing remains inherently contextual, each file representing a unique case. Nevertheless, many operations can be streamlined through a programmatic approach. The injection of metadata, already discussed, is a prime example. Likewise, the normalisation or targeted enrichment of elements within the `<music>` section can be implemented via custom scripts embedded in workflows that are both automated and adaptable, thereby aligning with the specific methodologies and objectives of each research project.

Therefore, it is important not to underestimate the usefulness of programming tools. Their almost infinite potential means that human investment can be significantly reduced, and many tasks that go far beyond the simple file generation can be automated. Consequently, it is necessary to first consider the overall digital resources a research project will require before deciding whether a programmatic approach would fit logically into the overall workflow. Automated tools are becoming more and more accessible in terms of use and operation (with the possible exception of systems based on deep learning), and the learning curve may not be as steep as it seems.

To complete this thought, it is also important that the didactic dynamics inherent in the digital humanities continue to develop. Collaborative educational platforms, such as the aforementioned SSH Open MarketPlace, are essential tools for promoting workflows and good practices. Their development is necessary to achieve a sufficient level of self-education. For the time being, MEI remains relatively unrepresented on any of these platforms (SSH Open MarketPlace, SSH Training Discovering Toolkit and even DARIAH-Campus). The official MEI site, however, offers tutorials on the basics of the XML language and the specific features of MEI. Musicologists might also find it useful to look at examples using external tools.

In conclusion, the diversity of tools for generating and manipulating MEI files is a rich resource that allows a workflow to be adapted to the specific needs of each project and user. This flexibility is evidence of the positive evolution of an open standard in musicology. If this progress is to continue, it is now essential that all musicologists from different backgrounds adopt the MEI and move beyond the sometimes arduous phase of discovering the tools. I hope that this article will provide guidance to those looking for answers and workflows to help them get started or explore new aspects of the MEI ecosystem.

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